

Validation of TRIPOLI-5[®] Monte Carlo code using the BEAVRS Benchmark

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ABSTRACT

TRIPOLI-5[®] is the new-generation Monte Carlo particle-transport code developed by CEA and ASNR, with the support of EDF, whose development started in 2022. The pilot version v0.1.0 has been released at the end of 2024. This version enables static isothermal calculations for neutrons (including the free gas model, thermal scattering laws, and probability tables). Elementary collision sampling has been extensively verified. The pilot version paves the way to code validation on full-core configurations. In this respect, we have selected the BEAVRS benchmark, whose detailed specifications and openly accessible measurement data make it ideal for this purpose. Models for TRIPOLI-5 and TRIPOLI-4 were generated, and comparisons were performed against OpenMC simulations and the available measurements, using ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0. In this work, we focus on the Hot Zero Power configuration, including critical boron concentrations, rod bank worth, and axial and radial fission distributions. Overall, an excellent agreement is observed, and the origin of the few discrepancies between codes have been identified.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Validation, BEAVRS, TRIPOLI-5

1. INTRODUCTION

TRIPOLI-5[®] is the new-generation Monte Carlo particle-transport code jointly developed by CEA and ASNR with the support of EDF in order to address nuclear reactor analysis, including multi-physics feedback for stationary and non-stationary configurations [1]. The first pilot version v0.1.0 has been released at the end of 2024. This version enables static isothermal calculations with a complete neutron collision physics, encompassing thermal scattering data, Doppler broadening of the elastic collision kernel using the Sampling of the Velocity of the Target nucleus (SVT) or the Doppler Broadening Rejection Correction (DBRC) models, and Unresolved Resonance Range (URR) treatment using probability tables.

In view of enhancing the reliability of TRIPOLI-5, an extensive verification and validation (V&V) campaign has begun. In this respect, the BEAVRS benchmark provides a great opportunity for the validation of reactor physics codes, in that it represents a full-core Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) model, encompassing fuel depletion on two operational cycles of a commercial nuclear power plant [2]. BEAVRS offers a high level of detail in the description of the geometry and the material compositions, as well as an extensive list of experimental measurements, and is publicly available through an MIT license [2,3].

In this work, we present the investigation of the BEAVRS benchmark in its stationary (beginning of cycle) isothermal configuration using TRIPOLI-5. We perform code-to-code comparisons with respect to TRIPOLI-4 [4] and OpenMC [5], and code-to-experiment comparisons using the data in Ref. 2.

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2. MODELING THE BEAVRS BENCHMARK

The BEAVRS benchmark includes the description of the reactor core and the structural components, including the core barrel, the baffle, the neutron shield panels and the reactor pressure vessel. The reactor core is composed of 193 fuel assemblies, each assembly being arranged in a 17×17 lattice containing uranium oxide (UO_2) fuel pins, 24 guide tubes and 1 instrumentation guide tube. The guide tubes may be empty or contain a burnable absorber rod or a control rod from one of the nine banks present in the core (A, B, C, D, SA, SB, SC, SD, SE). The instrumentation guide tube may also be empty, or it may contain an instrumentation tube which consists in a fission chamber. The core loading pattern presents three types of enrichment: high-enriched assemblies (3.1wt%) located on the periphery, low (1.6wt%) and mid-enriched (2.4wt%) assemblies grouped in a checkerboard pattern in the center. For a complete description, we refer to the benchmark specifications in Ref. 2. The OpenMC calculations were performed using the model provided in the public BEAVRS repository [3]. For TRIPOLI-5 and TRIPOLI-4, the models have been built from scratch for this work.

2.1. Verification of the geometrical models

The TRIPOLI-5 geometry was built using two different libraries: the native AGORA library [6] and the ROOT package developed at CERN [7]. For TRIPOLI-4, the ROOT geometry was re-used. The TRIPOLI-4 and TRIPOLI-5 models (geometry and materials) were built according to the benchmark specifications. Once created, the two models were carefully verified by performing preliminary comparisons against the OpenMC model.

The verification of the geometries was based on a tool querying the navigation routines of different codes or different navigation engines [6]. The first test consists in checking the material encountered in different geometries for a set of randomly distributed points in a given region. The comparison of both ROOT and AGORA geometries with respect to the one of OpenMC gave a percentage of error of **0.051%** on the entire geometry. All inconsistencies came from points located either on the top or the bottom spacer grids. In the OpenMC model, the top and bottom grid sleeves and grid spacers were made of stainless steel. However, this is inconsistent with the specifications, which state that *the top and bottom spacers consist of a Stainless Steel 304 (SS304) sleeve with Inconel internal structures* [3]. In order to be comparable with the OpenMC geometry, we have considered a second model with both AGORA and ROOT. This model was made with top and bottom grids fully in stainless steel. For this geometry, the percentage of error dropped to **0%** for all the cells.

In addition, comparisons of chord lengths were performed: for a set of random (isotropically distributed) oriented segments, we verified that in both models a particle would travel the same track, i.e. encounter the same sequence of materials with corresponding lengths [6]. This helps in identifying potential overlaps in a geometry, and ensures that the particle transport will be equivalent independently of the chosen geometry. The comparison on a set of 10^5 trajectories gave respectively one and two inconsistent trajectories for AGORA and ROOT. The inconsistencies were of the order of 10^{-6} cm, and no overlap was identified after a careful investigation. Thus, these inconsistencies were neglected, as resulting from numerical precision issues, and both AGORA and ROOT geometries were considered as verified. For the sake of illustration, radial and axial views of the AGORA geometry are provided in Figure 1.

2.2. Verification of the material compositions

For all defined materials, compositions were verified, and atom densities were compared one-to-one. The discrepancies between the compositions were all below 0.01%, except for two materials. The 'air' material in TRIPOLI-4 and TRIPOLI-5 exhibited concentrations 10 times higher than the correspond-

Figure 1. Radial (left) and axial (right) views of the BEAVRS core using the AGORA model.

ing composition in OpenMC. The density of air was apparently incorrect in the OpenMC model: the script said $0.000616 \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$, instead of the value $0.00616 \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$ provided in the specifications (which is coherent with the expected order of magnitude). The density of the ‘air’ composition was thus corrected in the OpenMC model definition. The second outlier was the ‘fuel’ composition (in all four fuel materials): an offset of 8% in the ^{234}U concentration was observed. This is likely due to the different method used by OpenMC to define the fuel compositions: the method `add_element` uses an optional enrichment parameter to set the fuel composition in uranium. To avoid this discrepancy, the OpenMC model was corrected and fuel materials were defined using lists of nuclides, and their corresponding atom fractions, as derived from the specifications. After the two corrections listed before, **the relative differences in the isotope concentrations from both models always stayed below 0.01%**, which corresponds to the precision level given by the specifications. This confirms the good agreement between both definitions of the materials.

3. CRITICAL BORON CONCENTRATIONS

The benchmark provides different core configurations, i.e. different insertion levels of control rods banks, with the associated measured critical boron concentrations. Our simulations were thus performed for the boron concentrations corresponding to the measured critical boron concentrations from the benchmark, and the multiplication factor k_{eff} was compared to the theoretical value of 1.

Calculations were performed using TRIPOLI-4, TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC, with ENDF/B-VII.1 [8] and ENDF/B-VIII.0 [9] nuclear data libraries. All the calculations were performed using 350 cycles, 1 million neutron histories per cycle, and 150 inactive cycles. The probability tables for the URR were read from ACE files for TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC, and from CALENDF for TRIPOLI-4.

The values obtained from the simulations for the multiplication factor are presented in Table I. It appears that the three codes rarely match the expected $k_{eff} = 1$, independently of the chosen library. Nonetheless, they follow the same behavior with respect to the control rods insertion routine. Especially, after the insertion of the bank D rods, the estimated value for the multiplication factor decreases, as more rods are

inserted into the reactor core. The agreement between the three codes is quite good with ENDF/B-VII.1.

Table I. Computed values of k_{eff} for ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Description	ENDF/B-VII.1			ENDF/B-VIII.0		
	TRIPOLI-4	TRIPOLI-5	OpenMC	TRIPOLI-4	TRIPOLI-5	OpenMC
ARO	0.99844 ± 0.00006	0.99809 ± 0.00009	0.99846 ± 0.00007	1.00041 ± 0.00006	0.99999 ± 0.00009	0.99940 ± 0.00008
D in	0.99992 ± 0.00005	0.99971 ± 0.00009	0.99993 ± 0.00009	1.00197 ± 0.00005	1.00114 ± 0.00009	1.00118 ± 0.00007
C, D in	0.99910 ± 0.00006	0.99882 ± 0.00008	0.99875 ± 0.00007	1.00091 ± 0.00006	1.00019 ± 0.00008	1.00000 ± 0.00007
B, C, D in	0.99783 ± 0.00005	0.99751 ± 0.00009	0.99780 ± 0.00009	0.99963 ± 0.00006	0.99920 ± 0.00009	0.99874 ± 0.00008
A, B, C, D in	0.99724 ± 0.00006	0.99685 ± 0.00008	0.99704 ± 0.00008	0.99875 ± 0.00006	0.99831 ± 0.00009	0.99798 ± 0.00008
Se, A, B, C, D in	0.99702 ± 0.00006	0.99673 ± 0.00010	0.99691 ± 0.00008	0.99842 ± 0.00005	0.99773 ± 0.00009	0.99746 ± 0.00009
Sd, Se, A, B, C, D in	0.99640 ± 0.00005	0.99611 ± 0.00009	0.99637 ± 0.00008	0.99773 ± 0.00005	0.99726 ± 0.00009	0.99692 ± 0.00008
Sc, Sd, Se, A, B, C, D in	0.99553 ± 0.00006	0.99505 ± 0.00009	0.99546 ± 0.00007	0.99678 ± 0.00006	0.99616 ± 0.00009	0.99578 ± 0.00008

For ENDF/B-VIII.0, TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC show a good agreement, as both estimations remain within their respective three sigmas uncertainties. However, a systematic discrepancy is detected: TRIPOLI-5 overestimates the multiplication factor compared to OpenMC, by $\approx +30$ pcm. This discrepancy is due to the different default parameters in the SVT model, see Section 3.1. On the other hand, TRIPOLI-4 appears to systematically overestimate by 40 to 80 pcm compared to TRIPOLI-5 with ENDF/B-VIII.0. In TRIPOLI-4, the threshold for thermal scattering laws is set by default to 4.95 eV, while in TRIPOLI-5 this threshold is the maximum energy for the inelastic thermal scattering found in the nuclear data files (about 10 eV for ENDF/B-VIII.0), which leads to the discrepancies discussed in Section 3.2.

3.1. Epithermal Broadening of the elastic scattering kernel

By default, the three codes apply the Sampling the Velocity Target nucleus (SVT) method. In TRIPOLI-5, the method is applied on all nuclides between 10^{-5} and $400k_B T$ eV (with T the temperature of the material, and k_B the Boltzmann constant). In OpenMC, the same conditions are applied on all nuclides, except for ^1H , for which the SVT range is extended to 20 MeV.

To test the impact of these parameters on the all rods out (ARO) configuration, we modified the SVT application range for ^1H in TRIPOLI-5 to match the OpenMC parameters. To further decrease the statistical uncertainty, we used 500 cycles, 200 inactive cycles and 5 million neutrons per cycle. Results for the multiplication factors are given in Table II: it appears that, when applying the same conditions for the SVT model, TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC are in excellent agreement. Also, the 30 ± 4 pcm overestimation is recovered when applying the SVT model up to $400k_B T$ for ^1H , which explains the systematic difference observed in Table I.

Table II. Effect of different SVT application range on k_{eff} for the ARO configuration.

OpenMC	TRIPOLI-5	TRIPOLI-5 with OpenMC range
0.99960 ± 0.00003	0.99998 ± 0.00003	0.99968 ± 0.00003

In addition, we investigated the impact of using the Doppler Broadening Rejection Correction (DBRC) model [10] instead of the SVT model. By default, TRIPOLI-5 applies the DBRC model from 10^{-5} eV to $400k_B T$ eV, which corresponds to around 20 eV at 600 K, while OpenMC applies DBRC from 0.01 eV to 1000 eV. As shown in Table III, this difference in terms of application range induces a 40 pcm discrepancy on reactivity. In addition, suppressing SVT altogether induces a reactivity effect of the order

of ~ 170 pcm compared to the case where SVT is used.

Table III. Effect of Doppler Broadening Rejection Correction on k_{eff} for different parameters. The * indicates that the range applies to all nuclides except ^1H which goes up to 20 MeV.

Method	Parameters	Range [eV]	OpenMC	TRIPOLI-5
DBRC	OpenMC default	0.01 – 1000	0.99915 ± 0.00003	0.99922 ± 0.00003
DBRC	TRIPOLI-5 default	$10^{-5} - 400k_B T$	×	0.99959 ± 0.00003
SVT	OpenMC default	$10^{-5} - 400k_B T^*$	0.99960 ± 0.00003	0.99968 ± 0.00003
None	-	-	1.00133 ± 0.00003	1.00137 ± 0.00003

3.2. Thermal Scattering Laws threshold

As mentioned earlier, TRIPOLI-4 imposes a fixed 4.95 eV upper threshold for the use of TSL. On the other hand, TRIPOLI-5 applies the TSL on their full energy range. In order to substantiate our analysis, we temporarily modified TRIPOLI-5 so as to mimic the behavior of TRIPOLI-4. Two configurations were tested after the modification: the ARO configuration and the bank D inserted state one, since this configuration shows the largest discrepancy. Table IV gives the results for both configurations with the modified version of TRIPOLI-5, denoted TRIPOLI-5*. Non-modified values for the k_{eff} obtained with TRIPOLI-4 and TRIPOLI-5 are recalled. The discrepancy between TRIPOLI-4 and TRIPOLI-5* calculations drastically decreases when applying the same threshold on the TSL energy range. Taking into account the respective standard errors, TRIPOLI-4 and TRIPOLI-5* appear to be in perfect statistical agreement, meaning that the TRIPOLI-4 overestimation using ENDF/B-VIII.0 is due to the issue with the TSL threshold.

Table IV. Impact on k_{eff} of the TSL threshold for two configurations.

Description	TRIPOLI-4	TRIPOLI-5	Difference TRIPOLI-4/TRIPOLI-5 [pcm]	TRIPOLI5* 4.95 eV threshold	Difference TRIPOLI-4/TRIPOLI-5* [pcm]
ARO	1.00041 ± 0.00006	0.99999 ± 0.00009	42	1.00031 ± 0.00009	10
D in	1.00197 ± 0.00005	1.00114 ± 0.00009	88	1.00199 ± 0.00009	2

3.3. Inconsistency in the top/bottom grid sleeves material

In order to evaluate the impact of the discrepancy in the top and bottom grid sleeves and grid spacers materials, mentioned in Section 2.1, we ran both configurations. Table V shows that there is a 16 pcm variation in k_{eff} , with a standard error of 8 pcm, meaning that this discrepancy has a negligible impact on reactivity. As the presence of inconel should not return any inconsistency, further investigations may be envisaged in the future.

4. CONTROL RODS BANKS WORTHS

As prescribed in [2], the control rod worth (noted Γ_{CR}) can be estimated based on

$$\Gamma_{CR} = \frac{k_0 - k_1}{k_1 k_0}, \quad (1)$$

Table V. k_{eff} for three geometrical models using TRIPOLI-5.

Model	Material in top/bottom grid sleeves	k_{eff}
AGORA	Inconel	0.99983 ± 0.00008
ROOT	Inconel	0.99985 ± 0.00009
AGORA	Stainless steel	0.99999 ± 0.00009

with k_0 being the multiplication factor before the control rods insertion at the critical boron concentration, and k_1 the multiplication factor after the rods insertion (keeping the same boron concentration). In addition to the criticality calculations performed in Section 3 (which yield the values of k_0), new simulations were performed to obtain the value of k_1 for each control rod. The rod worth estimations were performed with ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear libraries, using 350 cycles, 150 inactive cycles, and 1 million neutrons per cycle.

Table VI describes the rod worths and the difference with respect to the measured values along with the one-sigma standard error. It appears that all results are in good agreement: all bank worths agree within three sigmas, and in most cases even within one. The computed values are coherent with the experimental measurements. Banks C, B, A are however slightly overestimated by the three codes with ENDF/B-VIII.0, and the same is observed for banks C and B for ENDF/B-VII.1.

Table VI. Experimental and computed values of the control rod worths (in pcm) for ENDF/B-VII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Description	Experimental	ENDF/B-VII.1			ENDF/B-VIII.0		
		TRIPOLI-4	TRIPOLI-5	OpenMC	TRIPOLI-4	TRIPOLI-5	OpenMC
D	788	791 ± 8	800 ± 13	791 ± 11	784 ± 8	779 ± 14	770 ± 11
C with D in	1203	1242 ± 7	1254 ± 13	1256 ± 12	1262 ± 8	1245 ± 12	1284 ± 11
B with C, D in	1171	1238 ± 9	1236 ± 12	1215 ± 11	1228 ± 8	1208 ± 13	1220 ± 10
A with B, C, D in	548	575 ± 8	566 ± 13	571 ± 12	583 ± 8	606 ± 13	599 ± 11
Se with A, B, C, D in	471	490 ± 8	477 ± 12	470 ± 11	485 ± 8	495 ± 12	489 ± 11
Sd with Se, A, B, C, D in	772	802 ± 8	798 ± 14	808 ± 11	794 ± 8	790 ± 12	787 ± 13
Sc with Se, Sd, D, C, B, A in	1099	1117 ± 8	1126 ± 14	1139 ± 12	1109 ± 8	1132 ± 12	1122 ± 11

5. FISSION RATES IN INSTRUMENTATION TUBES

The benchmark provides the signals from fission chambers inserted at 58 locations inside the core. In order to get fission rates in the active part of the instrumentation tube, the air material filling this active volume was slightly modified to include traces of ^{235}U . This allows tallying reaction rates using the track-length estimator, in order to reach sufficient statistics despite the low density of air. Calculations were performed with ENDF/B-VIII.0 for OpenMC and TRIPOLI-5, with 500 cycles, 200 inactive cycles, and 5 million neutrons per cycles. Due to limitations in computing time, TRIPOLI-4 simulations were done with 700 cycles, 200 inactive cycles, and 1 million neutrons per cycle.

Figure 2 presents on the left the relative difference between the radial distributions of the fission rates computed with TRIPOLI-5 and the measurements. It is worth noting that the radial map of the fission chambers signals was initially tilted in the benchmark data (despite the fuel loading map being perfectly symmetric). In order to provide symmetric data as a reference for the simulations, the benchmark authors generated a tilt-corrected version of the fission distribution, which we adopted for our comparisons. The agreement between TRIPOLI-5 and the benchmark fission distribution is quite satisfactory,

with a relative difference ranging between -4% and $+4\%$, with a relative Monte Carlo standard error around 0.5% . On the right, Figure 2 presents the axial fission distribution in the E9 assembly, computed with the three codes and compared to measurements. Overall, a good agreement is observed with satisfactory consistency.

Figure 2. Left: Relative difference of the radial fission distribution computed with TRIPOLI-5 and tilt corrected measurements. Right: Axial fission distribution.

Figure 3 provides the comparison of the radial fission distributions of TRIPOLI-5 with respect to OpenMC on the left, and to TRIPOLI-4 on the right. The agreement is very satisfactory: relative differences are comprised between -2% and $+2\%$, again with Monte Carlo standard error of 0.5% on these values. It may seem that the distributions of the relative differences are tilted, however this is a statistical effect. Simulations were additionally run with different seeds, and different maps were obtained with a constant $\pm 2\%$ range for the relative differences.

Figure 3. Relative difference of TRIPOLI-5 fission rates to OpenMC (left) and to TRIPOLI-4 (right).

6. CONCLUSIONS

In view of building the verification and validation database of TRIPOLI-5, we adopted the BEAVRS benchmark, which models a full-scale pressurized water reactor, and we focused here on its static isothermal hot-zero-power state.

Simulations were performed for a critical state with various control rod positions and boron concentrations, and control rod banks worths. Radial and axial fission distributions were estimated. Each quantity was compared against experimental data and against the results of the Monte Carlo codes OpenMC and TRIPOLI-4. The choice of the DBRC or SVT model parameters, and the energy threshold of thermal scattering law were found to lead to apparent discrepancies in reactivity. Overall, a good agreement was found among codes and measurements, when consistently using the same nuclear data and simulation parameters. A similar analysis has been carried out using TRIPOLI-4 with a native geometry model [11]. Future work will concern the generalization of our TRIPOLI-5 simulations to hot-full-power states, including thermal-hydraulics feedback, and depletion.

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